

PEACEFUL CO-EXISTENCE IN NIGERIA: THE PERSPECTIVE OF CHRISTIANITY

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Abstract

Peaceful co-existence is what must be sought for, if Political, Economic, Religious freedom and development will be attained in Nigeria. Christianity enjoins Christians to co-exist peacefully with their fellow human beings. The great need of the Nigerian society more than ever before is peaceful co-existence. Since independence in 1960 there has been various unrests in Nigeria. The question is how, can people go about their normal business in this nation without peace and tranquility? The thrust of this paper, therefore, is on the Christian perspectives oil peaceful co-existence in Nigeria. It examines these perspectives and proffers useful suggestions as to how we can peacefully co-exist.

Keywords: *Peaceful, Existence, Christianity and Perspective.*

Introduction

Peace in no doubt a sine-qua-non to development. No society can really attain its economic and political heights when the ingredients of peace, harmony and social developments are lacking. Nigeria is a multi-religious, multi-ethnic nation and has been having its fair share in the distractions that come with its colouration. This is not to say that a multi-religious nation cannot progress, but a lot depends on the understanding and management of these differences as driven by political leaders.

Christianity has a great role to play on peaceful co-existence in Nigeria. Christianity is on the side of justice and peace, it has a great role to play in building peace among the citizenry. Christianity, as a religion, holds great

power and potency in re-ordering human lives and society, it has been used for good in human history. This is what gives motivation to this research, the study will define what is Christianity and peace, and examine how Christian perspectives could help to peacefully co-exist in Nigeria.

Definition of Terms

It may be needful to start by having definitions of the terms Christianity and Peace. Christianity is the standard of living founded in the blood of Christ and established in the Holy Scripture. It is that religion which survived Jesus Christ. It is a religion based on the teachings of Jesus Christ. A Christian is that individual who has accepted the Lordship of Jesus Christ. Christians strive to behave in the right ways because they love God and want to honour Him. It is essentially a way of life and not a dogma, creed or code of conflict. Christianity consists of the teaching and way of life made possible by the death, burial and resurrection of Christ.

Peace means absence of violence or other disturbances within a state. According to Encarta Dictionaries (2008), it means a state of tranquilly or quietness, freedom from civil disturbance. It is also a state of security or order within a community provided for by law or custom. This means freedom from oppressive thoughts o emotions, it deals with harmony ill personal relations.

The Oxford Dictionary of Current English (1996), defines co-existence as means of existing ill mutual tolerance of each other's ideologies.

Christianity and Peaceful Co-Existence

One of the major ingredients of national survival is peace. In fact, without peace, no meaningful development call be achieved by any nation. However, looking around, one sees a lot of things suggesting that we are far from having a peaceful atmosphere as a nation. Scarcely does a day pass without one hearing or reading of one violent crime or the other ill the nation.

In a dispensation of peaceful co-existence, the individual is respected and validated. The life and Ministry of Christ provides Christological foundations for the Christian involvement in peaceful co-existence. In deciphering the theological foundation for involvement in peaceful-co-existence, the radical prophetic imagination in the scripture cannot be ignored. God's prophets who denounced evil and oppression of the poor and marginalized Include-, Moses, Jeremiah, Micah, Amos, John the Baptist and John the Evangelist.

John the Baptist denounced corruption, oppression and victimization of the human person. This is why Christians cannot but be at peace with everybody in the society. Failure to do this crusade for a socially just and humane society is indeed a great failure and negligence on the part of the Christian. Inherent in Christianity are a lot of virtues that make for peace in the Christendom if honestly pursued. They include the following:

Peace with all men (Rom.10:18, Matt. 5-7)

Universal brotherhood of all (Luke 10:29-37)

Unconditional love to all mankind (ICor.13; John 13:34-35, Inn 4:20-21).

Patriotism and obedience to those in authority (Rms. 13:1).

God the author of life is against any system that negates peaceful co-existence. The Christian church has brought the wisdom of the Christian tradition into public conversation to complete to the well-being of society. Christianity has more than enough potentials to promote peace in Nigeria. To realize these potentials, it must not be applied in a parochial, myopic sense, aimed at serving some personal interest. Christianity, maintains that all human beings are equal in the sight of God and considers every human person as a special creation of God. It condemns corruption, dishonesty, injustice and disrespect to constituted authorities. This simply means that if and when the adherents of Christianity abide strictly by the tenets, we will be

able to achieve peaceful co-existence in the nation.

Sermons that are preached in churches with specific reference to citations from the Bible are efforts geared towards modifying the behaviour of the people positively in the society. The saying that 'the fear of God is the beginning of wisdom' always remains in one's mind such that will not make one to become a social miscreant engaging in thurgery, disorderliness and disruption of peace of the society. The counseling done by our Christian pastors is also a way in which our society can be made to maintain peace in the country.

For some people that do not always go to church, the use of radio and television, electronic media will be useful tools in communicating Christianity messages to them. When they listen to or hear these discussions that are being relayed on the radio and televisions, their hearts may be touched to the point thereby changing their attitude positively and having a moral and spiritual rebirth.

House to house fellowship and distribution of Christian tracts are vital roles in the maintenance of peace in Nigeria. There comes a time in the life of an individual or in the life of a nation, when as in the case of Paul on the road to Damascus, the conscience is pricked and the mind irrevocably turns away from evil. That turning point is well-nigh overdue in the lives of Nigerians. For once, Nigerians must with one accord, turn a new leaf and resolutely bid all the vices goodbye.

Christianity as a religion is the supreme manager of human imperfections and weaknesses. It regulates human behaviour by streamlining and mainstreaming the activities and values through processes and attitudes of individuals along with that of the larger society.

Conclusion

Ultimate peace is of God but as citizens of this nation, a religious nation, we all have prominent roles to play both individually and collectively. Emphasis has to be placed on the teaching of Christian morals. Dignity of labour has to be promoted, reward for hardwork, and adequate punishment for laziness, bribery and corruption. It is important that the entire populace must be peace conscious.

There is no doubt that ethnic and religious harmony and conflicts are destructive and would render real development a virtually unattainable dream. Therefore, the fact that the ever increasing peace challenges that we encounter in Nigeria today, a religious dimension should be a source of great concern for every adult Nigerian.

Recommendations

This paper has clearly elucidated that Christianity can play and has played a role in establishing peaceful co-existence in Nigeria. The following recommendations are made:

The Christian church should continue making interventions in the nation by issuing statements that call for peace.

Prayers composed by the church should be encouraged and prayed always. Among these prayers are: prayer against insecurity, and prayer for Nigerians in distress. Prayers like these are a good contribution to peaceful co-existence.

The pulpit of the Christian church has a great influence. The pulpit must be socially relevant and prophetically rooted. The prophetic-liberation tradition of scripture should involve all preaching.

We call on Christians and also on all people of good will to rally round the nation at this moment of great distress/crisis.

We have to recognize that the social and moral values of religion are indispensable assets for sustainable peace. We therefore, have to explore the positive aspects of religion in our people and use them effectively.

Let us speak peace and live peace, let us give peacefully a chance in Nigeria.

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The pulpit of the Christian church has a great influence. The pulpit must be socially relevant and prophetically rooted. The prophetic tradition of scripture should involve all preaching and teaching of individuals and the larger society. We call on Christians and also on all people of good will to rally round the nation at this moment of great distress/crisis.

REFERENCES

Encarta Dictionary (2009)

Oxford Dictionary of Current English(1996)

The Holy Bible (2008). Revised Standard Version. Bible Society Resources Ltd, China. Pp.4-223.